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1. Introduction

This Milestone concerns a virtual access to the cross-RI time series analysis service.

The service was described in the [Deliverable 5.5](#).

2. Service

The service is available at the address:

<https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-timeseries>

and is accessible through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access portal:

<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>

3. Service deployment timeline and evolutions

Since the service deployment in June 2023 (see [Milestone MS47](#)), a user panel was consulted twice:

- The first user panel was held in September 2023 (see [Milestone MS20](#))
- The second user panel was held in April 2024 (see [Milestone MS21](#))

The user panel consultations resulted in valuable feedback. Many of the propositions and remarks have been implemented and deployed, and most of the issues and bugs that were raised have been resolved. Among the most important improvements and evolutions of the service one can list the following:

- A detailed user guide was added (see <https://www.atmo-access.eu/atmo-access-time-series-analysis-service-help/> and Figure 1). It completes and updates an existing technical documentation contained in the [Deliverable 5.5](#).

Figure 1 User guide

- User interface ergonomics improvements, including:
 - o The map of stations, airports and regions was redesigned (see Figure 2):
 - The issue of overlapping stations and airports was resolved.
 - The map readability was improved.

Figure 2 The improved stations map

- The user interface of the “Select datasets” step was redesigned in order to improve the user workflow clarity. In particular, a colour legend for dataset’s variables was added (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 The improved “Select datasets” step

- A set of features for plot customization (changing a plot title, axes and legend annotations, axes scales, etc.) was added and documented in the user guide.

Moreover, since December 2023 an authentication mechanism has been added to the service. This allows the integration of the service into the common ATMO-ACCESS platform for monitoring the usage statistics of the ATMO-ACCESS services.